

tooth mark (definitive)

tooth mark (uncertain)

healing mark

matrix/broken

Supplementary Figure 1: Mark maps for isolated jugal specimens in lateral view. Abbreviations: or, orbit.

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Supplementary Figure 1 (continued): Mark maps for isolated jugal specimens in lateral view. Abbreviations: or, orbit.

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TMP 1998.081.0001
right lateral

TMP 1998.081.0001
right dentary

Supplementary Figure 2: Mark map for articulated jugal specimens in lateral/medial view. Abbreviations: d, dentary; j, jugal; I, lacrimal; m, maxilla; or, orbit; po, postorbital; pm, premaxilla; q, quadrate; qj, quadratojugal; sq, squamosal; R, right.